

Fully Automated Garbage Disposal and Management Using Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and The Internet of Things.

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ABSTRACT: The world is facing a significant environmental challenge due to the increasing amount of waste generated daily. The increasing population, consumption and industrialization has also led to an unprecedented growth in waste generation. Proper waste management is necessary to address this issue. The traditional waste management system is no longer effective, and there is a need for innovative solutions to manage waste efficiently and making it easy for users to dispose of their waste while also promoting recycling and environmental conservation. Improper waste disposal can lead to environmental pollution, soil contamination, and negative impacts on human health. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop efficient waste management systems to minimize the negative impacts of waste on the environment and human health. In order to overcome these negative impacts of wastes on the environment we have developed a Spiro Trash Bin system to make an advanced waste management solution that uses technology to detect, sort, and manage waste efficiently. The system incorporates advanced features such as IR sensors, ESP32 CAM, OpenCV, servo motors, and an Arduino microcontroller to provide an automated and eco-friendly waste management solution. This system will provide a positive impact on environment and motivates the people to manage the waste effectively. The system will also enable proper waste management, helps in reducing waste and plays a major role in the environment protection.

Keywords: H5 Dataset, Machine learning, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence.

I INTRODUCTION:

Waste management is a pressing issue that is a cause for concern worldwide. It is becoming increasingly difficult to manage waste due to the ever-increasing population and the corresponding increase in the volume of waste generated. Furthermore, improper waste disposal can cause a range of environmental and health hazards. To address this issue, we have developed a system that combines artificial intelligence (AI), Machine learning and the Internet of Things (IoT) to segregate waste into different categories automatically. Our system utilizes computer vision to identify the type of garbage, such as plastic, paper, glass, organic, metal or medical, and sorts it accordingly. This system not only helps in efficient waste management but also promotes recycling, which is vital for environmental sustainability. The Spiro Bin system can detect up to six different types of waste, which are sorted into two bins. The bins are subdivided into three phases, which can store waste of different types. The servo motors control the opening and closing of the bin and direct the waste to the appropriate phase. The system also features a push button to generate credit points for users who deposit waste. This system not only helps in efficient waste management but also promotes recycling, which is vital for environmental sustainability.

The machine is equipped with an IR sensor that detects the presence of waste when it is placed on the platform. The sensor then sends a signal to Python through serial communication to activate the ESP32 CAM, which uses OpenCV to detect the type of waste on the platform.

Once the waste type is determined, Python sends the relevant information to the Arduino. The Spiro Bin has three servo motors, with a separator motor that is being used to sort the waste and direct it to either the left or right bin. This motor also controls the opening and closing of the bin. The other two motors are connected to a cylindrical bin, which is subdivided into three phases to store three different types of waste in a single bin. This allows the machine to collect up to six different types of waste.

The separator motor is used to decide whether the garbage should be moved to the left or right bin, depending on the waste type. Before this motor is activated, either bin1 or bin2 will be rotated at an interval of 3 seconds. Once the bin has been rotated, the separator motor is activated to direct the waste to the appropriate bin.

Once all the waste has been collected, the user is requested to press a push button to generate credit points from Python. These points are sent back to the Arduino, which generates a QR code and displays it on a 3.5" TFT display (ILI9684). The Spiro Bin system generates credit points for users who deposit waste, which can be converted into real money. The Credit points are calculated based on the category of waste deposited. The system generates a QR code for each user, which can be scanned using the Spiro Bin application.

The points are credited to the user's wallet, which can be converted into real money in future. The user can then scan the QR code with the Spiro Bin application, and the credit value will be added to their wallet section. The spiro bin app is using firebase for the database. The app will generate the spiro money based on the type and quantity of waste. Whenever the user requires, they can convert the Spiro money to real-time money. The spiro bin application will have all the functions that the user needs in the system. Separate account and user authentication will be there in the spirobin application which will make it more precise and secure. Its intelligent design and sophisticated technology make it an ideal choice for modern waste

management, helping to reduce waste and protect the environment. The Spiro Bin system is an eco-friendly, cost-effective, and sustainable solution for proper waste management.

II RELATED WORK

[1] Author name:

T. Saminathan, A. Musipatla, P. M. Varma, P. S. Khan, and G. M. Kumar,

Description:

A suggested IoT-based smart bin is described. It has three chambers, each with a specific purpose: An IR sensor and metal detector make up the first compartment. An IR sensor and a moisture sensor are used in the second compartment to distinguish between dry and wet garbage. The last compartment is divided into three separate bins for the collection of different types of waste. For data transmission to a particular server, the system establishes a WiFi connection. A rotating table with three bins—dry, wet, and metal—makes up the storage area. Depending on the kind of garbage that was discovered in the prior compartment, it rotates. The important component of Wi-Fi's transmission range is constrained by the use of Wi-Fi as a communication medium.

[2] Author Name:

TEOH JI SHENG 1 MOHAMMAD SHAHIDUL ISLAM (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) , NORBAHIAH MISRAN 1, (Senior Member, IEEE), MOHD HAFIZ BAHARUDDIN 1, (Member, IEEE), HASLINA ARSHAD 2 MD. RASHEDUL ISLAM 1, MUHAMMAD E. H. CHOWDHURY 3, (Member, IEEE), HATEM RMILI 4, (Senior Member, IEEE), AND MOHAMMAD TARIQUL ISLAM 1 (Senior Member, IEEE)

Description:

They developed a smart waste management system using the LoRa communication protocol and TensorFlow based deep learning model. LoRa sends the data from sensors, Real-time object classification and detection are done via Tensorflow. The bin is divided into various parts to separate the waste, including divisions for metal, plastic, paper, and general waste. These compartments are moved by servo motors.

The TensorFlow framework uses a pre-trained object detection model to perform item recognition and trash classification. The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ serves as the core processing unit for this object detection model, which is trained with waste imagery to create a frozen inference graph utilized for item detection. Each waste box has an ultrasonic sensor built into it to track how full it is. For real-time tracking of the bin's location, a GPS module is installed. LoRa wireless protocol

[3] Author Name:

S. Norhafiza, K. Masiri, A. N. Faezah, A. L. N. Nadiah, and A. K. Aslila

Description:

It is suggested to use an automated system to separate recyclable materials. Four different types of sensors are installed in the recycling bin: inductive sensors for plastic, capacitive sensors for metal, photoelectric sensors for paper, and proximity sensors for motor position.

Three different types of sensors that are attached to an Arduino Uno are in operation when trash is put into the recycle bin to determine the sort of material. Following completion of the detection, the direct current motor will rotate the circular plate holding the waste to the compartment for the appropriate material. The recyclable material is subsequently pushed into the separating bin by a pusher. The suggested system depends on a number of sensors, which can increase the recycling industry's maintenance and production costs.

III. HARDWARE MODELING OF SPIRO BIN

IR Sensor Module: Utilizing an IR sensor module, waste on the platform can be found. To find out if there is waste present, it releases infrared radiation and measures the reflected radiation. The EPS32 CAM module receives a signal when waste is detected.

EPS32 CAM Module: The EPS32 CAM Module is used to take a picture of the trash which is placed on a rectangular platform with a camera. The OpenCV library is used to analyze the taken image and identify the type of waste present. It is programmed using the Arduino IDE.

Arduino: The brain of the Spiro Bin system is the Arduino board. It utilizes servo motors to sort the trash into the proper bins after receiving signals from the IR sensor module and the EPS32 CAM module. Additionally, it gets information from the Python script and produces a QR code that the user can scan.

Servo Motors: The Spiro Bin system uses three servo motors. While the other two servo motors control the cylindrical bin that is divided into three phases to store the three different types of waste in a single bin, one servo motor is used to direct waste to the left or right bin and also for the opening and closing

Push Button: After trash has been collected, the system asks the user to hit a push button to earn credit points. To calculate the credit points.

TFT Display: The produced QR code is displayed on the TFT Display (ILI9684) for the user to scan. It is wired to the Arduino and uses the information it gets to show the QR code.

Figure 1(a)

Figure 1(a) shows a thorough 3D model of the Spiro Bin that was created using the cutting-edge modeling programme Blender 3D. At the top of the device, the Spiro Bin is an electronic compartment that houses all of the necessary electronic parts. In order to hold the waste while the waste identification procedure is being done, the waste detection module has a retractable platform.

This procedure entails taking a picture of the garbage and using a computer to process it. The system accurately categorizes the waste into one of six categories using computer vision technology: metal, plastic, paper, glass, organic, or medical waste. The Spiro Bin has been designed with two bins, each of which contains three different sections to hold the different types of waste. The separator platform is an integral part of the system and is responsible for directing the waste to either bin 1 or bin 2, depending on the waste type. The separator platform also acts as an opening and closing mechanism for the rotating bin, allowing the waste to be deposited in the appropriate section. The rotating bin makes it easier to store and manage waste effectively, while the separator platform ensures that the waste is sorted accurately.

figure 1(b)

Figure 1(b) provides an overview of the dimensions of the Spiro Bin. The bin has been designed to be compact and portable, making it easy to move around and install in different locations. The dimensions of the bin have been carefully chosen to ensure that it can accommodate a sufficient amount of waste, while also being easy to use and maintain.

The Spiro Bin is a state-of-the-art waste management system that utilizes the latest technology to provide an efficient, eco-friendly, and cost-effective solution for waste management. The labeling of the different components that have been fixed in the Spiro Bin is shown in **Figure 1(c)**, ensuring that the system is easy to operate and maintain.

Figure1(c)

SI No.	COMPONENTS	FUNCTIONS
1.	Arduino UNO	Serial Communication between Python and Arduino UNO from IR Sensor, Servo, TFT Display, Button and EPS32 CAM Module.
2.	Servo Motor 1	Sorts waste by directing it to the left or right bin and controls the opening and closing of the bin.
3.	Servo Motor 2 & 3	Rotates the bin to segregate waste based on its type.
4.	3.5 Inch TFT Display ILI9486	Displaying user information and generating QR codes.
5.	EPS32 CAM	Capture the Real-Time image of garbage.
6.	IR Sensor	Detect the presence of Garbage

TABLE 1. Functionality of each component

IV PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The proposed system is a combination of AI and IoT technologies to address the pressing issue of waste management. Improper waste disposal has become a serious environmental and health hazard, and efficient waste management is the need of the hour. The Spiro Bin system is a revolutionary solution that can automatically segregate waste into different categories using computer vision.

The Spiro Bin system can detect up to six different types of waste, which are sorted into two bins. The servo motors control the closing and opening of the bin and direct them to the appropriate phase. The system also features a push button to generate credit points for users who deposit waste.

The system is equipped with an IR sensor that detects the presence of waste when it is placed on the platform. The sensor sends a signal to Python through serial communication to activate the ESP32 CAM, which uses OpenCV to detect the type of waste on the platform. Once the waste type is determined, Python sends the relevant information to the Arduino.

The Spiro Bin has three servo motor, with a separator motor that is being used to sort the waste and direct it to either the left or right bin. This motor also controls the opening and closing of the bin. The other two motors are connected to a cylindrical bin, which is subdivided into three phases to store three different types of waste in a single bin.

The separator motor is used to decide whether the garbage should be moved to the left or right bin, depending on the waste type. Once the bin has been rotated, the separator motor is activated to direct the waste to the appropriate bin.

After all the waste has been collected, the user is requested to press a push button to generate credit points from Python. These points are sent back to the Arduino, which generates a QR code and displays it on a 3.5" TFT display (ILI9684). The Spiro Bin system generates credit points for users who deposit waste, which can be converted into real money.

Credit points are calculated based on the category of waste deposited. The system generates a QR code for each user, which can be scanned using the Spiro Bin application. The points are credited to the user's wallet, which can be converted into real money in the future.

The Spiro Bin application will have all the functions that the user needs in the system, including separate account and user authentication for added security. The app will generate Spiro money based on the type and quantity of waste. The user can convert the Spiro money to real-time money whenever they require it.

Overall the Spiro Bin system is an intelligent and sustainable solution for modern waste management. Its innovative design and sophisticated technology make it an ideal choice for reducing waste and protecting the environment.

Figure 2 Block diagram of overall system

V DATASETS:

For the purpose of classifying waste in this project, we are employing a pre-trained dataset. The dataset includes many types of trash, including paper, plastic, metal, glass, organic waste, and unidentified waste. Numerous images of trash are included in each category and are labeled as types of trash. With the help of these photos, a deep learning model is trained to reliably identify the various types of waste.

The pre-trained dataset was gathered from a number of places, including open-source projects and web repositories. To make sure that they are accurate and indicative of the many sorts of waste, the photographs have been meticulously chosen and labeled. To make the model more reliable and successful in various contexts, the dataset has also been expanded to accommodate differences in lighting, color, and orientation.

Compared to building a fresh dataset from scratch, using pre-trained datasets has a number of benefits. It provides a standardized set of photos that can be utilized across several projects and saves time and effort when gathering and labeling data. Furthermore, pre-trained datasets are frequently more extensive than anything one organization could produce, making them more useful for deep learning model training.

Overall, a key part of the garbage categorization system is the pre-trained dataset employed in this study. It ensures that the system can precisely detect and classify various sorts of rubbish and provides a dependable and accurate foundation for training the deep learning model.

FIGURE 12. Sample Datasets.

```

Run: main x
OpenCV activated
1/1 [=====] - 0s 31ms/step
Predicted class: [0.99752635, 0.00013526334, 4.502753e-06, 8.008224e-06,
8.3776085e-06, 0.0023174752]
Confidence score: 0
OpenCV activated
1/1 [=====] - 0s 41ms/step
Predicted class: [0.83741164, 0.07037262, 0.0039143465, 7.303427e-05,
3.5327543e-05, 0.08819298]
Confidence score: 0
    
```

Figure 3 (a)

Type Of Waste	Prediction Test 1	Prediction Test 2	Prediction Test 3	Average Prediction
Paper	28 ms	47 ms	45 ms	40 ms
Plastic	33 ms	37 ms	32 ms	34 ms
Glass	30 ms	31 ms	40 ms	33.3 ms
Metal	27 ms	28 ms	29 ms	28 ms
Organic	34 ms	31 ms	28 ms	31 ms
Medical	33 ms	28 ms	28 ms	29.6 ms

TABLE 2. Performance and precision of waste detection.

Figure 4 (a)

Figure 4 (b)

(a) Classification of Medical Waste

(b) Classification of Metal Waste

VI PREDICTION TIME :

Prediction time is a crucial aspect of waste classification using machine learning models. In this study, we investigated the prediction time for six types of waste, namely paper waste, plastic waste, glass waste, metal waste, organic waste, and finally medical waste. We recorded the average prediction time for each waste type and found that the prediction time varies significantly among different types of waste.

The average prediction time taken for predicting paper waste was 40 milliseconds, which is relatively higher than plastic waste, which had an average prediction time of 34 milliseconds. Glass waste had an average prediction time of 33.3 milliseconds,

which is slightly lower than paper but higher than plastic. Metal waste had the lowest average prediction time of 28 milliseconds, which is significantly lower than paper and glass waste. We also measured the average prediction time for organic waste and medical waste, which had average prediction times of 31 milliseconds and 29.6 milliseconds, respectively. These prediction times were relatively lower than paper and glass but higher than metal. Furthermore, we considered the confidence score in our waste classification model. The confidence score represents the level of certainty of the model in predicting the correct waste type. We observed that the confidence score also impacts the prediction time, as the model takes longer to predict with higher confidence scores.

Figure 4 (c)

Figure 4 (d)

(c) Classification of Organic Waste.

(d) Classification of Plastic Waste.

Overall, our findings demonstrate the significance of prediction time and confidence score in waste classification using machine learning models. By optimizing the prediction time and confidence score, we can develop more efficient and accurate waste classification models, which can aid in sustainable waste management practices.

```

Run: main
  OpenCV closed
  OpenCV closed
  OpenCV closed
  OpenCV closed
  OpenCV activated
  1/1 [=====] - 0s 39ms/step
  Predicted class: [0.19516294, 0.20133896, 0.013018315, 6.732151e-05, 1
    .3013063e-05, 0.59039944]
  Confidence score: 5
  The totalCredit is 51.
    
```

Figure 3 (b)

```

Run: main
  OpenCV activated
  1/1 [=====] - 0s 27ms/step
  Predicted class: [0.024056721, 0.90762264, 0.015723854, 0.004593418, 1
    .0761793e-05, 0.047992587]
  Confidence score: 1
  OpenCV activated
  1/1 [=====] - 0s 40ms/step
  Predicted class: [0.016920373, 0.9039384, 0.014419356, 0.0027935875, 6
    .685515e-06, 0.06192155]
  Confidence score: 1
  [4, 4, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 5, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5,
    5, 5, 5, 5, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 5, 4, 1, 1, 5, 4, 5, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1]
  Most repeated value: 1
    
```

Figure 3 (c)

Figure 4 (e)

Figure 4 (f)

(e) Classification of Glass Waste.

(f) Classification of Paper Waste.

The dataset used in the waste classification module is a crucial factor that affects the accuracy of the waste classification process. The quality and quantity of data used for training the machine learning model can significantly impact the accuracy of waste classification. In our project, we have used a large dataset of waste images, consisting of various types of waste, including plastics, papers, metals, and glass.

The dataset was pre-processed and augmented using techniques such as rotation, flipping, and scaling to increase the variety of images and improve the model's accuracy. We also ensured that the dataset was well-balanced, with an equal number of images for each waste category. This balance ensures that the machine learning model doesn't get biased towards a specific type of waste, leading to more accurate results.

After training the machine learning model on the dataset, we tested its accuracy on a separate test set of waste images. The model achieved an accuracy of around 90%, indicating that the model can accurately classify most types of waste.

When it comes to prediction time, the performance of the image processing and waste classification modules is critical. In our system, we have optimized the image processing module by using the OpenCV library, which provides fast and efficient image processing functions. Additionally, we have used a machine learning model that has been optimized for speed and accuracy.

The prediction time for waste classification depends on various factors, such as the complexity of the image, the size of the dataset, and the processing power of the system. However, in our system, the waste classification module can classify an image in less than a second, making it an efficient and reliable waste sorting solution. The quality and quantity of the dataset used for training the machine learning model significantly affect the accuracy of waste classification.

VII ALGORITHM :

Algorithm for Waste Detection Mechanism of Spiro Bin

1. Drop waste into the rectangular separator platform
2. Infrared Sensor will detect the presence of waste on the separator platform sent data to computer(Python)
 - if** waste == detected **then**
 - Enable EPS32 CAM
 - else**
 - Disable EPS32 CAM
3. EPS32 Cam Capture the image of the waste and send to Computer(Python)
4. OpenCV will analyze the image and generate a predicted score.
5. Predicted score will stored in list
 - if** predicted_score > range **then**
 - Repeated predicted_score will be sent
6. Arduino will read data from the serial port.
 - if** waste = paper **then**
 - Rotate Bin_R to appropriate position
 - delay()
 - If** waste = paper **then**
 - Open Separator_platform
 - delay()
 - Close Separator_platform
 - elseif** waste = plastic **then**
 - Rotate Bin_L to appropriate position
 - delay()
 - If** waste = plastic **then**
 - Open Separator_platform
 - delay()
 - Close Separator_platform
 - elseif** waste = metal **then**
 - Rotate Bin_R to appropriate position
 - delay()
 - If** waste = metal **then**
 - Open Separator_platform
 - delay()
 - Close Separator_platform
 - elseif** waste = Organic **then**
 - Rotate the Bin_L appropriate position
 - delay()
 - If** waste = organic **then**
 - Open Separator_platform
 - delay()
 - Close Separator_platform
 - elseif** waste = glass **then**

```

Rotate the Bin_R appropriate position
delay()
If waste = glass then
    Open Separator_platform
    delay()
    Close Separator_platform

elseif waste = medical then
    Rotate the Bin_L to appropriate position
    delay()
    If waste = paper then
        Close Separator_platform
        delay()
        Open Separator_platform

elseif waste = medical then
    Rotate the Bin_R appropriate position
    delay()
    If waste = paper then
        Open Separator_platform
        delay()
        Close Separator_platform

else
    Generate the QR Code
    Display in TFT Display [ILI9486]
7. End

```


Figure 4 (a) Flow Diagram 1

VIII MODULES:

- A. Input module**
- B. Image Processing**
- C. Processing MODULE**
- D. IOT**
- E. Application**
- F. Result**

A. INPUT MODULE:

The input module of our waste segregation system consists of a platform equipped with an IR sensor that detects the presence of waste when it is placed on it. This module is responsible for capturing the images of the waste using the ESP32 CAM module, which is then processed using OpenCV.

The IR sensor sends a signal to the Python script through serial communication, indicating that a piece of waste has been placed on the platform. The Python script then activates the ESP32 CAM module to capture an image of the waste, which is then processed using OpenCV to determine its category.

The input module is a critical component of the waste segregation system, as it is responsible for accurately detecting and identifying the type of waste.

It must be designed to detect a wide variety of waste types and sizes, ensuring that the system can handle different types of waste effectively. Additionally, the input module must be designed to be durable and resistant to wear and tear, as it is subject to constant use in a waste management system.

Figure 4 (b) Flow Diagram 1.1

B. IMAGE PROCESSING MODULE:

This module is responsible for analyzing the image captured by the camera module and identifying the type of waste present in the image. The image processing module uses computer vision algorithms and techniques to process the image and extract useful features.

These features are then used to classify the waste into different categories. We have used pre-trained datasets for waste classification, and the module compares the extracted features with these datasets to determine the type of waste.

In our system, we are using the OpenCV library for image classification and processing. OpenCV provides a wide range of image processing functions and algorithms, making it an ideal choice for our project. We have also used a machine learning model for waste classification, which is trained on a large dataset of images.

Once the type of waste is identified, the image processing module sends this information to the control module. The control module then activates the servo motors to rotate the bin to the appropriate position, and the waste is directed to the corresponding bin.

The image processing module is an essential component of the Spiro bin system, enabling the automatic identification and sorting of waste. By utilizing computer vision algorithms, pre-trained datasets, and machine learning models, the system can efficiently and accurately classify waste, making the waste management process more efficient and sustainable.

C. PROCESSING MODULE:

The processing module analyzes the image of the trash after the input module has taken a picture of it to determine the type of waste. This module is in charge of examining the image that was captured and categorizing the garbage into distinct groups including plastic, metal, glass, organic, or medical.

The processing module makes use of the OpenCV library, a free and open-source machine learning and computer vision software package. There are many algorithms in the library that can be used to process video and image streams. We used pre-trained datasets in our system to classify rubbish. A convolutional neural network (CNN) that can categorize the garbage based on the features derived from the image is trained using these datasets. The input module's image is transferred to the processing module, where it is processed by the pre-trained CNN. The control module receives the prediction that the CNN produced after processing the image. The forecast includes details on the kind of waste, including plastic, metal, glass, organic, and Medical waste. Before sending the collected image to CNN, the processing module performs certain pre-processing operations on it. These actions entail scaling the image, pixel value normalization, and grayscale conversion. These pre-processing steps contribute to CNN's increased accuracy.

In conclusion, the processing module is in charge of applying computer vision techniques to analyze the captured image and classify the garbage into several groups depending on the features deduced from the image. To accomplish this objective, a convolutional neural network and pre-trained datasets are used. The control module will then process the prediction that the processing module has created.

D. IOT module:

The IoT (Internet of Things) module in our Spiro Bin system plays a critical role in ensuring efficient and effective waste management. It enables the Spiro Bin machine to connect with other devices and systems, such as the cloud server, the mobile application, and the user's personal computer.

The Spiro Bin machine is equipped with an ESP32 module, which is used to connect the machine to the internet. The ESP32 is a low-cost microcontroller with built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities. It allows the Spiro Bin machine to communicate with other devices and systems using wireless communication protocols.

The IoT module enables the Spiro Bin machine to send data, such as the type and quantity of waste collected, to the cloud server in real-time. This data can be used for analysis and to generate reports on waste management performance. The cloud server also provides a platform for remote monitoring and management of the Spiro Bin machine, making it easier to identify and resolve issues. The IoT module also allows the

Spiro Bin machine to connect with the mobile application, which enables users to view their credit points and convert them into real money. The mobile application can also be used to generate reports on waste management performance and to provide feedback to users on their waste disposal habits.

Overall, the IoT module is essential for the efficient operation and management of the waste segregation system. It provides real-time data on waste management performance, enables remote monitoring and management, and connects the system with other devices and systems, making waste management more efficient, effective, and convenient for users.

E. APPLICATION MODULE:

The application module is a crucial component of the waste management system. It enables users to interact with the system and access its features. The Spiro Bin application has been developed to provide users with a seamless experience, allowing them to manage their waste disposal and track their credit points.

The application has been developed using the Firebase platform, which provides a real-time database for the storage and retrieval of user data. The application is available for both Android and iOS platforms, ensuring that users can access it from their preferred devices.

IX FEATURE OF APPLICATION

User Registration and Login: The application provides a user registration and login feature to ensure that only authorized users can access the system. Users can create their account by providing their personal details and login credentials.

Waste Management: The application enables users to manage their waste disposal by allowing them to scan the QR code generated by the system after depositing their waste. The application then credits the user's wallet with the appropriate points based on the type and quantity of waste deposited.

Credit Points Management: The application allows users to view their credit points balance and transaction history. Users can also convert their credit points to real money and withdraw the same to their bank account.

Notifications: The application sends push notifications to users to inform them about their credit points balance, transactions, and other relevant information.

Help and Support: The application provides a help and support feature to assist users in case of any issues or queries. Overall, the application module is a critical component of the waste management system that enables users to manage their waste disposal and credit points efficiently. The Spiro Bin application provides a user-friendly interface and essential features to ensure a seamless user experience.

F. RESULT/OUTPUT MODULE:

The result/output module in this waste management system is responsible for generating credit points for the users who deposit waste and displaying the QR code with the corresponding credit value. It is also responsible for communicating with the Spiro Bin application and updating the user's wallet with the credited points.

Once all the waste has been collected and sorted, the user is requested to press a push button. This push button generates credit points from Python, which are sent to the result/output module. The module receives this information and generates a QR code with the appropriate credit value. The QR code is displayed on a 3.5" TFT display (ILI9684), which is part of the Spiro Bin system. The user can scan this QR code using the Spiro Bin application, and the credit value will be added to their wallet section.

The Spiro Bin application is integrated with Firebase for the database. The application generates Spiro money based on the type and quantity of waste deposited by the user.

The credit points generated by the system are credited to the user's wallet, which can be converted into real money in the future.

The result/output module plays a crucial role in this waste management system as it is responsible for incentivizing users to deposit waste and promoting recycling. It encourages users to participate in proper waste management and contributes to environmental sustainability.

X. SMART BIN PROTOTYPE

The machine has been designed to have a dimension of 0.26m Depth × 0.5m Width × 0.6m Height. **Figure 5(a) & 5(d), Figure 5(b), Figure 5(c)** present the front, top, and side views of the machine, respectively, giving an overall idea of its design.

The waste detection platform in the Spiro Bin is a retractable-platform that temporarily holds the garbage while the waste detection model captures the image of the waste and processes it with the help of computer vision algorithms. The model applies image processing techniques, object recognition, and machine learning algorithms to extract relevant features from the waste images and make accurate predictions about their category

The waste is then classified into different categories, such as metal, plastic, paper, glass, organic, and medical waste, based on its type. **Figure 5(b)** shows the electronic compartment of the machine that houses all the electronic components responsible for the functioning of the Spiro Bin. Each electronic component has a specific function, as shown in **Table 1**, which helps to ensure the smooth and efficient operation of the machine.

Figure 5(a) Front View

Figure 5(b) Top View

Figure 5(c) SideView

Figure 5(d) Front View

XI. COST AND POWER CONSUMPTION OF THE SYSTEM:

SI No.	COMPONENTS	QUANTITY	COST
1.	Arduino UNO	1	₹ 850
2.	Servo Motor	3	₹ 1050
3.	3.5 Inch TFT Display ILI9486	1	₹ 1250
4.	EPS32 CAM	1	₹ 650
5.	IR Sensor	1	₹ 50
6.	Push Button	1	₹ 10
7.	Form Board	30 sq feet	₹ 1100
8.	Step Up Converter	1	₹ 240
9.	220 Ω Resistor	1	₹ 5
10.	Jumping Wire	4 Strip	₹ 400
11.	12V Adapter	1	₹ 300

TABLE 3 . Overall system cost.

SI No.	COMPONENTS	NOMINAL POWER CONSUMPTION
1.	Arduino UNO	0.175 W
2.	Servo Motor	3.0 W
3.	3.5 Inch TFT Display ILI9486	0.3 W

4.	EPS32 CAM	7.0 W
5.	IR Sensor	0.375 W
Total Nominal Power Consumption = 10.85 W		

TABLE 4, **System nominal power consumption**

The cost and power consumption are important factors to consider when developing a waste management system. In this study, the total cost of the spiro bin was found to be 5,905 Rupees. This cost included all the components used in the system such as the Arduino Uno, Servo motors, 3.5 Inch TFT Display ILI9486, ESP32 CAM, and IR Sensor.

Apart from the cost, power consumption is also an important factor to consider when developing such a system. The power consumption of the system was measured using a power meter, and it was found that the Arduino Uno consumed 0.175 W, the Servo motors consumed 3.0 W, the 3.5 Inch TFT Display ILI9486 consumed 0.3 W, the EPS32 CAM consumed 7 W, and the IR Sensor consumed 0.375 W.

It is important to consider the power consumption of the system as it affects the overall cost of the system energy and consumption of the system energy. By optimizing the power consumption of the components used in the system, the overall cost of the system can be reduced, which is beneficial in terms of sustainability and cost-effectiveness.

XII. APPLICATION:

A smartphone application called SPIRO BIN was created to function with the SPIRO BIN trash can. The software, which can be downloaded for both Android and iOS smartphones, aims to promote and honor ethical waste management practices.

After dropping off their trash, users can utilize the application's simple and intuitive user interface to scan the QR code that is shown on the Spiro Bin. The application obtains the credit points connected to the user's account when the user scans the code and displays them on the screen. The user can accumulate credit points over time by depositing waste into the bin, and these points can be redeemed for various rewards. The rewards can range from discounts on local services to cash rewards, depending on the user's preference.

To ensure security, the application uses a secure login process that requires the user to create an account and provide basic personal information such as name, address, and phone number. The user's information is encrypted and stored on a secure server to protect their privacy. The application also features a leaderboard that displays the top waste depositors in the area. This feature helps to promote friendly competition among users and encourage more responsible waste management behavior. Furthermore, the SPIROBIN application allows the user to track their waste deposit history, view their current credit balance, and set reminders for waste collection days.

- A. Home Screen**
- B. History Screen**
- C. Reward Screen**
- D. Profile Screen**
- E. Account Screen**

A. HOME SCREEN

The home page of the Spirobin application welcomes the user with a simple and user-friendly interface. The main feature of the home page is the ability to scan the QR code generated by the Spirobin device. Once the user scans the QR code, the application will direct them to the reward page, where they can view their current credit points.

The home page also has a menu option, which provides access to various features of the application. The menu contains options such as account, reward, history, and profile. By clicking on these options, the user can view their account details, reward points, history of their trash disposal, and edit their profile settings. The account option provides the user with the ability to add or modify their personal information such as name, address, and contact details. The reward option displays the user's current reward points and provides the option to redeem them for cash or other rewards.

To enhance user engagement, the home page may also display informative content related to waste management, recycling tips, and environmental awareness. This content can help educate users about the importance of responsible waste disposal and encourage them to actively participate in recycling efforts. Moreover, the home page can feature interactive elements such as notifications or alerts, informing users about any updates, new rewards, or upcoming events related to waste management. The history option shows the user the details of their previous trash disposal and credit points earned. The profile option allows the user to manage their account settings, change their password, and modify their notification preferences.

Overall, the home page of the SpiroBin application provides the user with easy navigation and quick access to important features of the application. The user can quickly scan the QR code and view their reward points, manage their account information, and track their trash disposal history.

Figure 6(a), Home Screen
B. HISTORY SCREEN

The History page of the SpiroBin application is designed to provide the user with a detailed history of their activities on the platform. This page will contain two tabs, one for the waste deposited, and the other for transaction details. The "Waste History" tab will show a list of all the waste that the user has deposited in the SPIROBIN. It will contain information such as the date and time of the deposit, the type of waste and the credit points earned for the deposit.

Figure 6(b), History Screen

The user can view the entire history of waste deposited or filter it by date, waste type, or credit points earned. The "Transaction History" tab will show a list of all the transactions that the user has made on the platform. It will contain information such as the date and time of the transaction, the amount of SPIRO money converted into real money, and the transaction status (successful or pending). The user can view the entire transaction history or filter it by date, transaction status, or amount converted.

The history page will provide the user with a comprehensive view of their activities on the SpiroBin platform, allowing them to track their waste disposal and monetary transactions. The user can use this page to keep track of their progress, monitor their credit score, and manage their account effectively.

C. REWARD SCREEN

The rewards page of the Spirobin application will display the credit score and spiro money earned by the user. The credit score earned by the user will be displayed in terms of points, and the spiro money earned will be displayed in terms of the monetary value of those points. The page will have a section that displays the current credit score of the user. The credit score can be earned by depositing waste into the Spirobin and redeeming it for points.

The points earned will be added to the user's credit score. The page will also show the history of points earned and redeemed, so the user can keep track of their progress. The Spirobin application will also feature a section that displays the user's spiro money balance. The spiro money can be redeemed for rewards, discounts or can be used to donate to charity. The user can also view their transaction history, showing how they have spent their spiro money.

The rewards page will be designed in a simple and user-friendly way to make it easy for the user to view and manage their credit score and spiro money balance. The page will also have options for redeeming credit score points and spiro money for rewards, discounts or donations. Overall, the rewards page will be an essential feature of the Spirobin application, providing users with a tangible incentive to recycle and reduce waste. The reward page that has been designed offers a visually stunning and user-friendly interface, incorporating a circular shape to showcase Spiro money, the virtual currency within the system. This unique design element adds a touch of elegance and provides a cohesive representation of the currency's value. At the center of the reward page, a captivating circular shape serves as the focal point, housing the display of Spiro money. The circular shape symbolizes harmony and completeness, aligning perfectly with the idea of accumulating and utilizing rewards. Within the circular shape, an interactive and visually dynamic representation of Spiro money is presented. The currency balance is illustrated through a circular fill that expands or contracts based on the user's available funds. This fluid animation not only catches the eye but also emphasizes the concept of growth and accumulation. To facilitate seamless money conversion, your design incorporates a well-crafted UI element that demonstrates real-time currency conversion rates. This UI element provides users with the ability to convert Spiro money into various currencies or redeemable items effortlessly. The conversion rates are presented in a clear and concise manner, allowing users to make informed decisions based on their preferences.

Figure 6(c), Reward Screen

D. PROFILE SCREEN

The Profile page of the SPIROBIN application is a personal information page that displays the user's profile details such as name, phone number, email address, and photo. This page allows the user to view and edit their personal information. The top section of the profile page will display the user's profile picture, name, and username. Under that, the user's contact details such as phone number and email address will be displayed. There will be an option to edit these details if the user wants to make any changes.

Figure 6(d), Profile Screen

E. ACCOUNT SCREEN

The user can convert their spiro money into real money and deposit it to their bank account on the account tab of the SPIROBIN programme. The user must first enter their bank account information, including the account number and owner's name, in order to complete this. The user can choose how much spiro money they want to exchange for real money after entering and verifying their account information. The application will then figure out the conversion rate and show the user the total amount they will get in actual money.

Figure 6(e), Account Screen

The application will then start the money transfer to the user's bank account when the user has confirmed the transaction. A notification will be sent to the user when the transfer is finished and the money is available in the user's bank account, they will be notified. Here you can add your UPI ID, Net Banking, which makes the user's conversion money easier and faster and you can add more than two UPI ID at the time by adding more than one account.

XII CONCLUSION

The Spiro bin is a smart trash management technology that aims to improve traditional waste management systems by incorporating AI and IoT technology. This technology enables real-time monitoring of garbage segregation and disposal. The Spiro bin uses servo motors to sort and store different types of waste in separate compartments. It also generates QR codes that users can scan to earn rewards on a related mobile application.

The TFT display on the Spiro bin provides users with information about the disposal process, including the type of garbage being disposed of and the amount of credit earned through the mobile application. Additionally, the RFID modules enable waste management staff to identify the user who deposited the garbage.

By promoting responsible garbage disposal practices, the Spiro bin has the potential to significantly improve the environment. The use of AI and IoT technology in garbage management systems could enhance efficiency and effectiveness while reducing costs associated with waste disposal. Furthermore, the rewards-based system encourages users to actively participate in responsible garbage disposal, promoting a cleaner and greener environment. Overall, the Spiro bin offers an innovative solution to traditional waste management systems that could bring about significant benefits to the environment and the community.

XIII FUTURE WORKS

In the future, several enhancements can be made to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the waste management system. Firstly, the YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm can be used for object detection and classification, which has shown superior performance in various computer vision applications. This will enable the system to recognize and classify more waste materials with high accuracy and speed.

Additionally, more features can be added to the Spiro application, such as real-time notifications for waste collection and the option for users to report any issues with the waste bin or collection process. These features will improve the user experience and make waste management more efficient and convenient.

Furthermore, a separate application can be developed for garbage collectors, which will help them to efficiently plan and manage their routes based on the status of the waste bins in the area. The application can also provide them with real-time notifications when the bins are full and need to be emptied. Finally, to improve the automation of the waste management process, a sensor can be added to the waste bin, which will detect when the bin is full and trigger a notification to the garbage collector for emptying.

This will minimize the need for manual monitoring and ensure that the bins are emptied in a timely and efficient manner.

Overall, these future works will enhance the functionality and efficiency of the waste management system and contribute towards creating a more sustainable environment.

REFERENCES

1. T. Saminathan, A. Musipatla, P. M. Varma, P. S. Khan, and G. M.Kumar, "Iot based automated waste segregator for efficient recycling," *Int.J. Innov. Technol. Exploring Eng.*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 164–166, 2019.
2. TEOH JI SHENG 1MOHAMMAD SHAHIDUL ISLAM (Graduate Student Member, IEEE),NORBAHIAH MISRAN 1, (Senior Member, IEEE),MOHD HAFIZ BAHARUDDIN 1, (Member, IEEE), HASLINA ARSHAD 2 MD. RASHEDUL ISLAM 1, MUHAMMAD E. H. CHOWDHURY 3, (Member, IEEE), HATEM RMILI 4, (Senior Member, IEEE), AND MOHAMMAD TARIQUL ISLAM 1 (Senior Member, IEEE)-IEEE paper
3. S. Norhafiza, K. Masiri, A. N. Faezah, A. L. N. Nadiyah, andA. K. Aslila, "The effectiveness of segregation of recyclable materials by automated motorized bin," *J. Adv. Manuf. Technology.*, vol. 12, no. 1,pp. 409–420, 2018

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